

Application of DINA Model to Assess Omani and Iranian Fourth-Grade Students' Mathematics' Attributes

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The present research study aims to apply the deterministic input noisy output and gate (DINA) model for assessing Omani and Iranian fourth-grade students' mathematics attributes. All Omani and Iranian students who participated in the TIMSS 2015 mathematics fourth-grade assessment were selected as the statistical sample. To analyze the statistical data, the CDM package by the R programming was applied. The findings of parameter estimation revealed that many items could not fit the model well. However, about 25% of items' slipping index was higher than 0.50 which indicated the students who have possessed all attributes, have answered the items incorrectly. Furthermore, the RMSEA value for all items was below 0.05 excluding item 40. Hence, skill probabilities estimation specified that Iranian students' attribute probabilities were greater than Omani students.

Keywords: DINA, TIMSS, MATHEMATICS, PARAMETER ESTIMATION, CDM, ATTRIBUTE PROBABILITIES

Introduction

Applying educational assessment to evaluate students' achievements, for obtaining quite enough information about the reason for students' successes and failures has become an interesting topic for educational researches (Rahman Doust et al, 2021). Furthermore, applying new assessment approaches which are known for discovering detailed information about students' cognitive information has been more interesting.

The application of cognitive diagnostic models (CDMs) has been a quite strong analysis method in educational and psychological subjects. Moreover, cognitive diagnostic assessment (CDA) is introduced as a comparatively new method in education as well as psychological assessment to help in furnishing diagnostic data about participants' degree of dominance of variously defined sub-skills (Lee & Sawaki, 2009; Feng, 2013). The

cognitive diagnostic assessment provides a set of vital information about the weaknesses and strengths of test-takers in the field of knowledge and processing skills in such a way that examinees can discover the probability reasons for their success or failure and improve their future performance. In other words, arguing and relying on the total score of students' achievements do not provide a real picture and enough information on students' weaknesses and strengths (Dogan & Tatsuoka, 2008). Unlike classic test theory and item response theory methods that focus only on single overall scores of examinees to get information of their knowledge and learning process, the CDM approach is able to provide a set of information based on the defined attributes that show how well an examinee mastered or not mastered on an attribute. Furthermore, the reason for mastery or non-mastery could be explained by the CDM model (Li, 2016; Jang, 2008).

DINA Model

The deterministic inputs, noisy 'and' gate (DINA) is known as one of the CDM models which provides more advantages and it is well-known for CDM researchers. Furthermore, among the existing CDMs models that are being applied, the DINA model would be identified as the simplest CDMs model (Dela Torre, & Douglas, 2008; Sünbül, 2018; Fay, 2018). According to T. Oguz et al. (2013), the DINA model is known as a latent class approach which was introduced by Haertel (1989) initially. The DINA model categorizes examinees into two different latent traits in an item: **1. Compensatory**; to respond to an item, the examinees should possess all required attributes and **2. Non-compensatory**; the examinees lack at least one required attribute to answer the items correctly (De la Torre & Minchen, 2014; Jain, 2018; Terzi & de la Torre, 2018). In other words, the non-compensatory model such as DINA does not compensate for an absence attribute by another one. For instance, to answer an item that requires “**addition, subtraction, and multiplication**” the examinee should have mastery in all three skills to provide a correct answer (Feng, 2013). Furthermore, the DINA model provides slipping and guessing parameters for each item to estimate item parameters. In other words, item parameter analysis contained item discrimination index (IDI) to estimate slipping and guessing index, for each item independently (i.e., $\delta = 1 - g - s$). The IDI indicates how much an item would be answered correctly without the effect of guessing and slipping parameters by examinees (Kunina-Habenicht et al., 2009). Besides, the DINA model applies the root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) to identify how well a test item fits the model. Therefore, the items with an RMSEA index below 0.05 indicate a good fitting index while if the RMSEA shows an index above 0.05 and below 0.10, it indicates that the item would fit the model moderately. Furthermore, if the RMSEA illustrates an index above 0.10 and below 0.80, it would be concluded that the item-fitting index is reasonable and poor for the model. Consequently, an item with an index above 0.80, indicates that the model is not fitted (De la Torre et al, 2010). Though, the item discrimination index included guessing and slipping parameters. The guessing parameter demonstrates the percentage of examinees, who have not mastered all attributes but could offer an answer to the item correctly by guessing the parameter. Moreover, the slipping parameters illustrate the percentage of students who have possessed all attributes but answered an item incorrectly by the slipping parameter. Furthermore, if the IDI is close to 1, it identifies that the item is

appropriate. In other words, a high discrimination index indicates that the examinees have answered an item without guessing and slipping parameters (George & Robitzsch, 2015). Table 1 explains item parameter indices.

Table 1 the criteria item parameter estimates

Guessing	>0.5=very bad item
Slipping	Close to 1:=very bad item
IDI	Close to 1:=very good it
RMSEA	0.05=well fitted; >0.8 =not fitted; 0.05 & <0.8 =reasonable & acceptable

Objectives

1. To estimate the TIMSS 2015 fourth-grade mathematics item parameter for Omani and Iranian students.
2. To study Omani and Iranian fourth-grade students' mathematics attribute mastery level in the TIMSS 2015 mathematics items.

Related Work

Elbulok (2021) stated that the CDMs apply to drive out examinees' latent variables for the evaluation of students' skills. He concluded that the CDMs' major aim is to measure and assess multiple latent variables which are categorical. Akbay et al (2018) suggested that the defined attributes may do not indicate students' strengths and weaknesses. Furthermore, according to (Tatsuka, 1984, 1990) Akbay suggested, at least 8 attributes should be defined to determine examinees' proficiency level on a domain. Hence, Akbay concluded, relying only on the previous attributes may do not reveal reliable details and information of the students' mastery level. Li (2016) emphasized that the sample size could affect the validation of Q-Matrix. He suggested that to avoid the Q-Matrix invalidity, it is better to select a large sample size. Li also compared two Q-Matrices (1. designed by the researcher and 2. Estimated by model). The estimated Q-Matrix could fit the model better than the expert-designed Q-Matrix. According to Evran (2019), the CMDs are known as stronger models than traditional ones at evaluating approaches. Furthermore, Evran, indicated that among CDMs models, the G-DINA is a better fitting approach than the DINA model. Lee et al (2011) showed, the students who have low mastery proportion in skills, were able to respond to items correctly. However, Lee emphasized that some students had a high mastery proportion in skills, but they provided high incorrect respond to the items. Li & Lei (2015) compared a set of saturated CDMs to compare model fitting performance.

Afzali et al (2014) applied the DINA model to analyze mathematics items. The main findings of this study showed that the DINA model provides rich and fine-grained diagnostic information that can be directly applied to classroom instruction. Moreover, this study's results showed that Iranian students only possessed one attribute out of 8 attributes. The outcomes showed that among DIN, DINO, G-DIN, RRUM, and ACDM, the DINA and DINO had the worst fitting results. In other words, the DINA could not fit the model well.

Materials and Methods

The main purpose of the CDM is to specify the attributes which are known as latent variables. In the present

study, to determine the required attributes or skills for responding and solving TIMSS mathematics fourth-grade items, 8 cognitive attributes have been applied which were defined by Lee & Taylan, (2011) based on the TIMSS 2007 Mathematics Framework. In other words, Lee & Taylan determined 15 cognitive attributes, but as Akbay cited” (Tatsuka, 1984, 1990) suggested at least 8 attributes should be defined for students’ skill determination (Rupp & Templin, 2008b). Furthermore, since the size of the samples was large, applying all 15 attributes would take more time and require a broader research project (Wafa, 2019). Therefore, the researchers selected just 8 attributes for the present research study. All purposed samples have been taken from Omani and Iranian fourth-grade students who participated in the TIMSS 2015 assessment. In other words, 9105 Omani students and 3823 Iranian students have been selected as the statistical sample for the present study. Moreover, the DINA model has been applied to analyze the mathematics items to find out whether Omani and Iranian students have possessed the required attributes or not. The second aim of the study is to find out Iranian and Omani students’ weaknesses and strengths on the determined attributes. To analyze the data, the CDM package through the R programming, version 4.0.3, was applied.

Constructing Q-Matrix

The second step was taken to construct a Q-Matrix. The nature of the application of the CDMs requires the construction of a Q-Matrix for the defined attributes. To construct a Q-Matrix, several methods can be applied. In this study mathematics experts’ comments and loud-thinking methods have been used to develop a Q-Matrix for the defined attributes. Three mathematics’ teachers collaborated to determine the final required attributes for each item which were required for making a correct response for each item separately. All three teachers were females with 5, 10, and 7 years of teaching experience. Additionally, a second method also was applied for assurance of the construction of the Q-Matrix. The second step used the loud-thinking method. The loud-thinking method requires students to think loudly and express the strategies and steps while answering the items. Therefore, teachers note or record the entire process and decide what attributes are required for answering the items. One of the teachers was required to enquire her students to answer the items by the loud-thinking method and the process was recorded while the students were answering the items by loud-thinking method (the permission was taken from the students for video recording). The constructed Q-Matrix is presented as follow:

Table 2 Constructed Q-Matrix

Item	Knowing				Applying			Reasoning
	RG	CF	CM	RT	MR	DR	RP	AN
1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
2	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
3	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
4	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
5	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
6	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
7	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
8	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
9	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1

10	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
11	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
12	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
13	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
14	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
15	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
16	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
17	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
18	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
19	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
20	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1
21	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
22	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
23	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
24	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
25	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
26	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
27	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
28	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
29	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
30	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
31	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
32	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
33	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
34	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
35	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1
36	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
37	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
38	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
39	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
40	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
41	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
42	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0
43	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
44	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1

45	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
46	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
47	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1
48	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
49	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1
50	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1
51	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
52	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
53	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
54	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1
55	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
56	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
57	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
58	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1
59	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
60	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
61	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
62	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
63	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
64	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1
65	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1
66	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1
67	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1
68	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1

The purposed Q-Matrix was analyzed by” `din.validate.qmatrix(modle,print=TRUE)`” function through R programming. Hence, the DINA model also suggested an estimated Q-matrix. The DINA estimated Q-Matrix did not show any differences with the researchers-developed Q-Matrix. The above Q-Matrix included a set of rows and columns. The rows represent the required attributes for answering the items and the columns represent the number of the items. If an item requires the given attributes (in rows) for answering an item correctly, the “1” value would be allocated to the attribute, and if the item does not require the attribute, the worth of “0” would be given to the item. As an instance, one question has been written below:

M05-02. Which one of the given numbers is closer to 300?

- a). 275 b). 291 c). 307✓ d). 320

The above item’s q-matrix is defined as follows:

Item	RG	CF	CM	RT	MR	DR	RP	AN
M05-02	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1

The above table indicates that for answering the given item, five attributes are required which are: Recognize (RG), Classify (CF), Compute (CM), analyze (AN) and Determine (DR).

Findings

Item Parameter Estimation

Table 3 Item Parameter Estimation (DINA Model)

Oman	Iran
Deviance = 97458.92	Deviance = 39184.81
Log-Likelihood= -48729.1	Log-Likelihood = -19592.41
Number of iterations: 40	Number of iterations: 52
Number of item parameters: 136	Number of item parameters: 136
Number of skill class parameters: 255	Number of skill class parameters: 255
Information criteria:	Information criteria:
AIC = 98240.2	AIC = 39966.81
BIC = 100929.4	BIC = 42311.37
Mean of RMSEA item fit: 0.025	Mean of RMSEA item fit: 0.024

Table 3 contains the DINA model information like deviance, log-likelihood, iteration, AIC, and BIC for Omani and Iranian students' items.

Table 4 Item Parameter Estimates (DINA Model)

Model Fitting for Oman Data					Model Fitting for Iran Data				
Item	Guess	Slip	IDI	RMSEA	Item	Guess	Slip	IDI	RMSEA
1	0.454	0.094	0.452	0.016	1	0.349	0.172	0.479	0.018
2	0.324	0.165	0.511	0.026	2	0.347	0.095	0.558	0.040
3	0.241	0.299	0.460	0.023	3	0.085	0.529	0.386	0.017
4	0.127	0.450	0.422	0.017	4	0.068	0.584	0.348	0.040
5	0.085	0.290	0.625	0.014	5	0.229	0.313	0.458	0.020
6	0.263	0.159	0.578	0.006	6	0.338	0.045	0.617	0.010
7	0.182	0.330	0.488	0.033	7	0.167	0.336	0.497	0.025
8	0.136	0.334	0.530	0.037	8	0.285	0.164	0.551	0.030
9	0.328	0.272	0.400	0.018	9	0.117	0.646	0.237	0.008
10	0.163	0.486	0.351	0.021	10	0.140	0.667	0.193	0.021
11	0.194	0.517	0.289	0.021	11	0.242	0.471	0.287	0.024
12	0.496	0.075	0.429	0.011	12	0.242	0.584	0.174	0.013
13	0.214	0.245	0.541	0.019	13	0.130	0.370	0.500	0.011
14	0.552	0.102	0.347	0.017	14	0.576	0.083	0.340	0.021

15	0.241	0.256	0.503	0.005	15	0.211	0.247	0.541	0.013
16	0.054	0.514	0.432	0.005	16	0.155	0.429	0.416	0.010
17	0.004	0.919	0.077	0.002	17	0.003	0.849	0.148	0.008
18	0.073	0.667	0.260	0.009	18	0.063	0.859	0.077	0.004
19	0.204	0.655	0.141	0.005	19	0.140	0.747	0.114	0.007
20	0.541	0.376	0.083	0.013	20	0.211	0.537	0.252	0.008
21	0.425	0.167	0.408	0.014	21	0.320	0.353	0.327	0.013
22	0.208	0.416	0.377	0.005	22	0.338	0.247	0.415	0.008
23	0.443	0.143	0.414	0.011	23	0.321	0.169	0.509	0.012
24	0.167	0.512	0.320	0.010	24	0.204	0.653	0.143	0.012
25	0.000	0.801	0.200	0.044	25	0.000	0.752	0.248	0.036
26	0.099	0.558	0.343	0.002	26	0.047	0.600	0.353	0.005
27	0.289	0.153	0.558	0.014	27	0.220	0.172	0.608	0.030
28	0.360	0.464	0.176	0.021	28	0.351	0.471	0.178	0.019
29	0.092	0.702	0.206	0.030	29	0.028	0.905	0.068	0.015
30	0.213	0.433	0.354	0.025	30	0.187	0.388	0.426	0.029
31	0.038	0.673	0.288	0.045	31	0.011	0.738	0.252	0.026
32	0.107	0.625	0.268	0.018	32	0.100	0.640	0.260	0.028
33	0.185	0.371	0.444	0.017	33	0.200	0.518	0.283	0.023
34	0.588	0.118	0.294	0.020	34	0.627	0.117	0.256	0.015
35	0.118	0.475	0.408	0.026	35	0.087	0.462	0.451	0.018
36	0.220	0.646	0.134	0.030	36	0.173	0.711	0.116	0.035
37	0.115	0.345	0.540	0.037	37	0.461	0.128	0.411	0.022
38	0.333	0.234	0.433	0.026	38	0.344	0.428	0.228	0.033
39	0.466	0.052	0.482	0.010	39	0.511	0.073	0.416	0.017
40	0.488	0.028	0.484	0.068	40	0.131	0.780	0.089	0.019
41	0.197	0.366	0.436	0.036	41	0.290	0.456	0.253	0.032
42	0.299	0.526	0.176	0.030	42	0.270	0.530	0.200	0.040
43	0.085	0.663	0.252	0.037	43	0.000	0.930	0.070	0.015
44	0.029	0.735	0.235	0.019	44	0.037	0.867	0.096	0.020
45	0.215	0.619	0.166	0.061	45	0.169	0.605	0.226	0.046
46	0.008	0.641	0.351	0.035	46	0.004	0.866	0.130	0.016
47	0.271	0.326	0.404	0.034	47	0.225	0.482	0.293	0.043
48	0.099	0.766	0.135	0.023	48	0.062	0.676	0.262	0.043
49	0.229	0.235	0.536	0.049	49	0.426	0.080	0.494	0.072
50	0.260	0.269	0.472	0.019	50	0.159	0.303	0.538	0.011
51	0.291	0.422	0.287	0.049	51	0.266	0.379	0.355	0.090
52	0.059	0.501	0.440	0.036	52	0.001	0.954	0.045	0.012
53	0.526	0.065	0.409	0.051	53	0.413	0.124	0.463	0.064
54	0.328	0.318	0.354	0.037	54	0.258	0.555	0.187	0.042
55	0.414	0.068	0.518	0.014	55	0.493	0.060	0.447	0.012
56	0.277	0.410	0.313	0.013	56	0.211	0.532	0.257	0.016

57	0.260	0.573	0.167	0.025	57	0.237	0.625	0.138	0.026
58	0.312	0.072	0.616	0.049	58	0.460	0.069	0.471	0.068
59	0.323	0.167	0.509	0.075	59	0.102	0.363	0.535	0.025
60	0.275	0.478	0.246	0.039	60	0.300	0.524	0.175	0.027
61	0.298	0.380	0.322	0.025	61	0.248	0.622	0.130	0.023
62	0.167	0.578	0.254	0.032	62	0.173	0.767	0.061	0.019
63	0.254	0.339	0.407	0.019	63	0.200	0.517	0.283	0.017
64	0.126	0.431	0.443	0.026	64	0.193	0.357	0.450	0.028
65	0.303	0.269	0.428	0.023	65	0.320	0.166	0.514	0.022
66	0.317	0.168	0.514	0.044	66	0.190	0.377	0.433	0.011
67	0.048	0.530	0.422	0.021	67	0.026	0.495	0.479	0.004
68	0.059	0.765	0.175	0.008	68	0.014	0.782	0.204	0.008

Table 4 presents Omani and Iranian students' item parameter estimation analysis results which was analyzed by R programming (CDM package). The Omani students' results showed that the Items 11 ($s=0.517$), 12 ($g=.496$), 14 ($g=0.552$), 17 ($s=0.919$), 18 ($s=0.667$), 19 ($s=0.655$), 20 ($g=0.541$), 25 ($s=0.801$), 26 ($s=0.558$), 28 ($s=0.464$), 29 ($s=0.702$), 31 ($s=0.673$), 32 ($s=0.625$), 34 ($g=0.588$), 36 ($s=0.646$), 42 ($s=0.526$), 43 ($s=0.663$), 44 ($s=0.735$), 45 ($s=0.619$), 46 ($s=0.641$), 48 ($s=0.766$), 53 ($g=0.526$), 57 ($s=0.573$), 62 ($s=0.578$), 67 ($s=0.530$) and 68 ($s=0.765$) were identified as very bad items. In other words, the items' IDI values were lower than 0.30 and guessing and slipping parameters were above 0.50 for Omani students' mathematics test items. It seemed, many items' slipping index was higher than 0.50 which indicated, the students who possessed all attributes, answered to the items incorrectly. However, the IDI value for the items 2, 5, 6, 8, 13, 15, 27, 37, 49, 55, 59 and 66 was above 0.50 that indicated, these items considered as the good items. In other words, the higher IDI value was belonging to the item 5 which showed, just only 0.085 of examinees who have not mastered in all attributes, answered the correctly by guessing parameter. Besides, the RMSEA value for all items showed an index below 0.05, except the items 40 (RMSEA=0.068), 45 (RMSEA=0.061), 59 (RMSEA=0.075). The Iranian students' item parameter analysis results revealed that the items 3 ($s=0.529$), 4 ($s=0.584$), 9 ($s=0.646$), 10 ($s=0.667$), 12 ($s=0.584$), 14 ($g=0.576$), 17 ($s=0.849$), 18 ($s=0.859$), 19 ($s=0.747$), 20 ($s=0.537$), 24 ($s=0.653$), 25 ($s=0.752$), 26 ($s=0.600$), 29 ($s=0.905$), 31 ($s=0.738$), 32 ($s=0.640$), 33 ($s=0.518$), 34 ($s=0.627$), 36 ($s=0.711$), 39 ($g=0.511$), 40 ($s=0.780$), 42 ($s=0.530$), 43 ($s=0.930$), 44 ($s=0.867$), 45 ($s=0.605$), 46 ($s=0.866$), 48 ($s=0.676$), 52 ($s=0.954$), 54 ($s=0.555$), 56 ($s=0.532$), 57 ($s=0.625$), 60 ($s=0.524$), 61 ($s=0.622$), 62 ($s=0.767$), 63 ($s=0.517$) and 68 ($s=0.782$) were recognized as bad items. These items' IDI value was below 0.30 and guessing and slipping indices showed an index above 0.50. Moreover, the beset IDI value belonged to the items 2, 6, 8, 13, 15, 23, 27, 50, 59, 65. Though, the RMSEA values for all items were below 0.05, except the items 49 (RMSEA=0.072), 51 (RSMEA=0.090), 53 (RSMEA=0.064) and item 58 (RSMEA=0.068). Subsequently, the items 17, 18, 19, 20, 25, 26, 29, 31, 32, 34, 36, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 48, 57, 62, and 68 were defined as bad items for both Oman and Iran. Nevertheless, the IDI values for items 2, 5, 6, 8, 13, 15, 27, 59, were above 0.50 which indicated, these items were considered as good items for both Omani and Iranian students.

Mean of the Indices

To sum up, the Omani and Iranian students' item parameters indices' mean have been analyzed in table 5.

Table 5 the Mean of Indices

Mean of Oman Indices				Mean of Iran Indices			
Guessing	Slipping	IDI	RMSEA	Guessing	Slipping	IDI	RMSEA
0.24	0.39	0.37	0.025	0.21	0.47	0.31	0.024

The mean of guessing, slipping, IDI, and RMSEA of Omani and Iranian item parameters analysis indicated that the DINA model was fitted well for both counties (**Oman**, RMSEA= 0.025; **Iran**, RMSEA= 0.024). The mean of slipping and guessing parameters showed that 24% of Omani and 21% of Iranian students answered the items by guessing parameters without possessing all attributes. Furthermore, 39% of Omani and 47% of Iranian students responded to the items despite having mastery in all required attributes. Besides, the mean of the IDI values of the Omani and Iranian students showed 0.37 and 0.47 respectively.

Skill Probabilities

The DINA model offers examinees' parameters estimation statistics, which refers to determining how many of the examinees have a chance to possess the attributes. The attribute probability follows $C(2^A)$, where "A" demonstrates the number of probability attributes that examinees have a chance to possess. According to the above equation and the number of attributes in the present study (8 attributes), there are 255 latent classes for 8 attributes. The percentiles of the attributes have been illustrated in table 6 and figure 1.

Table 6 Skill Probability

Oman		Iran	
Attributes	Skill Probabilities	Attributes	Skill Probabilities
RG	0.59	RG	0.67
CF	0.67	CF	0.74
CM	0.66	CM	0.74
RT	0.66	RT	0.72
MR	0.67	MR	0.71
DR	0.63	DR	0.67
RP	0.66	RP	0.70
AN	0.68	AN	0.76

Figure 1 Skill Probability

Table 6 and figure 1 identify that Iranian students’ skill probabilities were higher than Omani students. However, the highest skill mastery probability was the same skill for both Iranian and Omani students which were: **Analysis (Iran; =0.754), (Oman; =0.675)**. Furthermore, both Omani and Iranian students showed high mastery proportion on “**Analysis**” skill rather than other skills. Nevertheless, the lowest mastery proportion for both countries was “**RG (recognize)**”, **Iran: (RG=0.666); Oman: (RG=0.589)**. Consequently, Iranian students’ mastery level was greater than Omani students in **RG**. Additionally, to show the attribute class profiles for Omani and Iranian students, 10 top highest attribute profiles have been selected to present in this study. Table 6 and figures 3 and 4 represent the skills’ class profiles.

Table 7 and figures 3 and 4 show the Omani and Iranian students’ mathematics skill class profiles. The attribute pattern (1111111) represents the number of skills in the present study (8 skills).

Table 7 Skills Class Profiles

Oman			Iran		
Mastery Pattern	Probability	Frequency	Mastery Pattern	Probability	Frequency
00111111	0.003	23	11111110	0.001	4
11111110	0.008	5	11111101	0.012	7
11111101	0.013	92	11111011	0.01	5
11111011	0.006	39	11110111	0.02	2
11110111	0.008	54	11101111	0.01	34
11101111	0.012	83	11101111	0.01	58
11011111	0.022	154	11011111	0.004	26
10111111	0.010	75	10111111	0.01	25
01111111	0.003	22	01111111	0.004	11
11111111	0.28	1973	11111111	0.39	1175

The skill class profile showed, 0.28 Of Omani students (1973 students) possessed all attributes, while this profiles pattern for Iranian students was identified, 0.39, (1175 students). Therefore, Iranian students’ mastery proportion was higher than the Omani students. Furthermore, the attribute pattern (01111111) indicates that the examinees lack at least 1 skill to possess. The pattern showed that just only 22 Omani students (0.003) and 11 Iranian students (0.004) possessed 7 skills and they did not master at least 1 skill.

Figure 2 Omani Students' Skill Class Profiles

Figure 3 Iranian Students' Skill Class Profiles

The lowest proportion of the attributes pattern for Omani and Iranian students is presented in table 8 and figure 4.

Table 8 the lowest Skills Class Profiles

Examinees profiles who have mastered in no skills					
Oman			Iran		
Mastery Pattern	Probability	Frequency	Mastery Pattern	Probability	Frequency
00000000	0.003	23	00000000	0.003	7

Figure 4 the lowest Skills Class Profiles

As presented in table 7, (0.003) 23 Omani students mastered none of the attributes as well as 7 (0.003) Iranian students did not master. It indicates that the Iranian students’ skill class profiles were better than Omani students. However, both Omani and Iranian students showed weaknesses in “**RG**” skill (Recognize). In other words, both Omani and Iranian students’ strength domain was in “**AN**” skill (Analysis).

Students’ Skill Classification based on Expected a Posterior (EAP) for Omani and Iranian Students

Omani Student’s Individual Skill Classification based on Expected a Posterior (EAP)

Figure 5 represents one Omani student’s skill classification based on EAP. Figure 5 illustrates one Omani student’s individual skills classification pattern. The figures indicating **item parameter plot** (the top plot, left-hand side), **skills mastery probability plot** (the top plot, right-hand side), **skill class distribution** (the bottom plot, left-hand side), and individual classification for student number 1 (the bottom plot, right-hand side). The information of the plots showed that the student with ID number 1 with a cut-off of 0.60 did not master **RG** (Recognize), **MR** (Measurement), and **RP** (Represent/Model) skills. In other words, this student showed weakness in **Recognition, Measurement, and Represent/model** skills. The student with ID number 1 in the TIMSS 2015 mathematics assessment was a boy student.

Figure 5 Omani Student’s Individual Skill Classification based on EAP with ID Number 1

He was taken booklet number **04** and about his parents' educational level, his guardian had a university degree. Hence, he belonged to a small town or village school and the testing language was identified as English.

Iranian Student's Individual Skill Classification based on Expected a Posterior (EAP)

Figure 6 illustrates one Iranian student's skill classification based on EAP (student ID number 1). Figure 6 indicates that the student with ID number 1 individual skill classification. The given information illustrates that the student with ID number 1 did not master **RG** (Recognize), **RT** (Retrieve) **MR** (Measurement), and **RP** (Represent /Model). Furthermore, the student with ID number 1 from Iran was weak in these skills in mathematics. The student holding ID number 1 was a girl and her guardian completed lower secondary education. Furthermore, she was taken her test in the Persian language, and her school was located in a suburban area.

Figure 6 Iranian Student's Individual Skill Classification based on EAP with ID Number 1

Discussion

Very recently, the CDMs evaluation approaches have been employed to investigate students' psychological information. A variety of CDMs models have been applied to assess retrofit test items to find out examinees' fine-grade information. In other words, the CDMs are known as the approaches which can form a relationship between latent traits and students' ability to succeed in responding to a test item (De la Torre & Minchen, 2014). The present study aimed to apply the DINA model to assess Omani and Iranian fourth-grade students' mathematics items in the TIMSS 2015. To determine the required attributes a Q-Matrix was developed by the researchers in collaboration with three mathematics teachers. To estimate the item parameters, the DINA model was applied. The item parameter estimation analysis revealed that Omani students answered five items (item 12, 14, 20, 34, and 53) correctly without possessing all attributes. However, Iranian students answered two items (item 14 and 39) correctly by guessing parameters despite possessing all attributes. Besides, the item slipping parameter showed that 19 items were answered incorrectly by Omani students while they had possessed all attributes. Hence, Iranian students responded to 34 items incorrectly regardless to have mastery in all attributes. The IDI index of the items showed that the highest IDI index belonged to item 5 which demonstrated only 0.085 Omani students could answer this item correctly by guessing parameter. Moreover, the highest IDI value belonged to item 6 which showed 0.33 of Iranian students responded to the item correctly by guessing parameter. Consequently, the RMSEA outputs of Omani students exposed, the items 40, 45, and 59 could not fit the model very well. However, it would be considered as a reasonable fitting index. In other words, items 49, 51, 53, and 58 found an RMSEA value above 0.05 which indicated the fitting was reasonable for Iranian students. The skill probability classification indicated that Iranian students' skill probability was higher than Omani students in all attributes. Additionally, the results of the study showed that, recognize skill (**RG**), identified as the lowest proportion than other attributes. To sum up, skills class profiles illustrated that 0.28 % of Omani students (1973 students) possessed all attributes (11111111) while Iranian students' profile showed 0.39 % of students (1175 students) mastered all attributes (11111111). Therefore, Iranian students' mastery proportion was higher than the Omani students' skill mastery profiles. In other words, only 23 (0.003) Omani students possessed none of the attributes as well as 7 (0.003) Iranian students did not master them. These findings were in contrast with Afzali et al (2014) and Minaei (2012). However, the researcher did not find any studies in Oman which was focused on the DINA model for analyzing mathematics attributes. Hence, Omani

and Iranian students had strength in Analysis skill (AN) and weakness in recognition skill (RG) in the TIMSS 2015 fourth-grade mathematics items.

Educational Implication of the Findings

The results of the study could be applied to educational matters. In other words, the CDM analysis showed, without considering students' cognitive abilities it is hard to provide a reasonable and acceptable conclusion of students' abilities in educational subjects, especially in mathematics. The educational materials should be designed based on the required skills in each subject and mathematics teachers should be trained to focus more on teaching and improving the mathematical attributes and skills which are more crucial to fulfilling mathematics learning objectives.

Conclusion

The present study focused on driving out a comparison look between two countries' students' skills' competency in mathematics that both of them are located in the Middle East. The Omani students' testing language was Arabic and English and Iranian students' language was only Persian. Both countries have been participating in the TIMSS assessment for many years. The DINA model revealed that it could be applied as a valuable and more beneficial cognitive diagnostic model to analyze large assessment data. In other words, the model was able to analyze the data very well. Hence, most of the students could possess the attributes. However, most of the students made incorrect answers to the items despite having mastery of the required attributes. To sum up, the item parameter analysis revealed that Omani students' IDI index could provide a better distinguish between students with high and low abilities than Iranian students.

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